

Open Science Champion

ASAP Open Science Policy Handbook

A Comprehensive Reference Guide for the ASAP
Collaborative Research Network (CRN)

ASAP Open Science Policy Handbook

Executive Summary

The Aligning Science Across Parkinson's (ASAP) Open Science Policy Handbook is a comprehensive reference guide. It provides fine-grained detail and unambiguous explanations of what ASAP expects from its grantees in the Collaborative Research Network (CRN) in terms of open science. This document constitutes the official ASAP CRN Open Science Policy, itemizing all requirement specifications around policy compliance within our five (5) overarching requirements. Each item within an overarching requirement outlines a specific action that a grantee can take to comply with the Policy and lays the foundation for ASAP to have a consistent compliance monitoring and enforcement workflow. External-facing documentation summarizing the Policy can be found on the [ASAP website](#), [this checklist for authors](#), and [these guidance documents](#).

The overarching goal of the ASAP Open Science Policy is for scientific findings that stem from ASAP funding to be verifiable and for the associated research outputs to be reusable. Practically speaking, this means that someone looking at a figure panel from an ASAP-funded study should be able to identify and reuse the data that underlie that figure, the code used to analyze those data, and the lab protocol and key lab materials used to collect those data (Requirements 1 and 2). The other sections aim to ensure that this information is shared in a timely and open manner (Requirement 3), that ASAP is acknowledged (Requirement 4), and that a comprehensive record of ASAP-funded outputs exists and is shared within the ASAP Collaborative Research Network at an early stage (Requirement 5).

This document comes with an accompanying [glossary](#). Every time a keyword first appears in this document, we provide a link to the section of the glossary that outlines how this document is using that term. To improve clarity, this document italicizes words that refer to the level of our policy (e.g., *require*, *recommend*; see [glossary](#)).

The Policy aims to cover a broad range of research disciplines, and we acknowledge that special circumstances may arise. Grantees may request exemptions by emailing openscience@parkinsonsroadmap.org with a clear justification.

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Overview of the Policy Requirements

The ASAP Open Science Policy is divided into five (5) overarching requirements:

1. **Share research outputs.** Data, code, and protocols generated as part of an ASAP-funded study must be deposited in a community-recognized repository by the time of posting a preprint, with accompanying information to facilitate reuse of those outputs and a license that allows for reuse. Key lab materials generated as part of an ASAP-funded study must be registered for an identifier by the time of posting a preprint.
2. **Identify research inputs.** Data, software, protocols, and key lab materials used in a study—but which were not generated as part of an ASAP-funded study—must be unambiguously identified.
3. **Ensure immediate open access.** Preprints must be posted no later than the date a manuscript is submitted to a journal for review. Preprints and publications must be immediately publicly available with a CC BY license or CC0 public domain dedication and include an Availability Statement and Key Resources Table (KRT) outlining where all research outputs (Requirement 1) and research inputs (Requirement 2) can be accessed.
4. **Acknowledge ASAP.** Manuscripts and other research outputs that were partially or fully funded by ASAP must acknowledge ASAP. Manuscripts must include an ORCID and a CRN author affiliation for CRN researchers.
5. **Share outputs with the ASAP network.** All ASAP-funded research outputs, including manuscripts, must be promptly shared on the ASAP CRN Hub. Manuscript drafts must be sent to the ASAP Open Science Team through the ASAP CRN Hub no later than the time of posting a preprint.

1. Share Research Outputs

Summary. Data, code, and protocols generated as part of an ASAP-funded study must be deposited in a community-recognized repository by the time of posting a preprint, with accompanying information to facilitate reuse of those outputs and a license that allows for reuse. Key lab materials generated as part of an ASAP-funded study must be registered for an identifier by the time of posting a preprint.

1.1. Data

- 1.1.1. *Required. Raw data* (see [glossary](#) for definition). Data must be deposited in their rawest reasonable form (e.g., the data have not been cleaned or preprocessed) in a discipline-specific, community-recognized repository that follows [FAIR principles](#). We acknowledge that, depending on the type of data and the repository used, some level of preprocessing or curation may be required before sharing.

Discipline-specific repositories are designed to hold specific data types (e.g., [CRN Cloud](#), [GEO](#), [Brain Image Library](#), [OpenNeuro](#)); and are in contrast to generalist repositories that can hold all data types (e.g., [Zenodo](#), [Dryad](#)). See [here](#) and [here](#) for recommended discipline-specific and generalist repositories. A non-exhaustive list of data types that we *require* to be deposited in a discipline-specific repository include: genetics, omics, neurophysiology, microscopy, images, MRI, fMRI, EEG, and PET, among others.

Deposited data must come with a persistent identifier (e.g., a Digital Object Identifier–DOI, or Accession Number) that is cited in the manuscript and Key Resources Table (KRT).

Data must be deposited by the time of posting a preprint. If the grantee has full control over making the deposit publicly available (e.g., as is the case for Zenodo, GitHub, and [protocols.io](#), among other repositories) then the deposit must be publicly available by the time of posting a preprint. If the grantee does not have full control over making the deposit publicly available (e.g., because some repositories, such as the CRN Cloud, only make data publicly available after completing quality control and curation) then the deposit must be publicly available as soon as the repository is ready to make them available (i.e., embargoing the release of data is *not permitted*).

Exception: If a discipline-specific, community-recognized repository does not exist for a data type, then the data, alongside a rich metadata description, can be deposited to a generalist repository.

Exception: If the researcher has already signed a Data Use Agreement (DUA) which explicitly prohibits the public sharing of raw data.

Exception: Sensitive data (see item 1.1.5).

- 1.1.2. **Required. Cleaned data** (see [glossary](#)). Cleaned data are the data entered into an analysis script and may represent the individual data points displayed in figures. Cleaned data used to produce all results, including figure panels, tables, graphs, and numbers presented in the results section of a manuscript must be deposited in a publicly accessible repository by the time of posting a preprint. This includes image quantification data. Cleaned data are often in tabular format and have often been preprocessed. It is possible, but unlikely, that the raw data and cleaned data will be the exact same.

Deposited data must come with a persistent identifier (e.g., a DOI) that is cited in the Key Resources Table (KRT). Datasets that include only summary data (e.g., means, standard deviations—see [glossary](#)) can be shared, but are not sufficient to meet this policy item. This item is in addition to item 1.1.1 (i.e., both raw *and* cleaned data must be shared).

Exception: Sensitive data (see item 1.1.5).

- 1.1.3. **Required. Tidy tabular data.** For data types that are stored in tabular format, the data must be deposited as a .csv file or another plaintext, non-proprietary equivalent (e.g., .txt, .tsv) and be in “tidy” format (guidance is available [here](#)). All the data should be contained within text. Color coding and text formatting are not retained in .csv files and are not best practice for data management. Each column must represent a single variable and each row must represent a single unit of observation. We also *require* that each variable be defined in a data dictionary, codebook, or README file.

- 1.1.4. **Required. Omics data.** All omics data must be deposited to [the CRN Cloud](#) by the time of posting a preprint. This includes genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics, and lipidomics data, among others. The CRN Cloud will then make the data publicly available after curation and quality control steps (i.e., the data do not need to be publicly available in the CRN Cloud at the time of posting a preprint). To submit omics data to the CRN Cloud, complete [this form](#).

Exception. If the omics data are already in [the GP2 database](#), you do not need to re-deposit the data to the CRN Cloud.

- 1.1.5. *Required. Sensitive data* (see [glossary](#)) must be deposited to the extent allowed by the associated research ethics approval (e.g., after anonymization, to a controlled repository). If the data can be openly shared, then we *require* these data be shared as described in items 1.1.1 and 1.1.2. If the data cannot be openly shared, but can be shared with restricted or controlled access (see [glossary](#)), then they must be shared as restricted or controlled data and come with instructions for how to request access to the data. It must be a data managing organization, rather than the individuals or lab that collected the data, that approves access requests.

Note: we *require* that grantees collecting data from human participants provide evidence that there has been satisfactory review and approval of the plan to collect and/or share such data from the appropriate ethics committee(s) (or evidence that no such approval is required).

- 1.1.6. *Required. Reuse license (data)*. Deposited data should come with a CC0 public domain dedication. Licensing data is different from licensing creative works—such as written manuscripts—and the CC0 public domain dedication allows for the most seamless reuse of data ([see here](#) for a detailed explanation). We also *permit* the CC BY license without a “ND”, “NC”, or “SA” modifier.
- 1.1.7. *Required. README file (data)*. Each data deposit must include a README file entitled “README”, located in the main folder of the deposit. README files must include sufficient information so that someone not part of the study team can access the data, determine which data correspond to which results (e.g., figure panels), and understand the data well enough to reuse them and appropriately merge them with data from other studies. Guidance is available [here](#). If a repository does not allow README files, the equivalent information must be shared in the appropriate metadata fields.
- 1.1.8. *Required. iPSC quality control table*. If iPSCs are used, an iPSC quality control table must be included in the associated manuscript or deposited to a publicly accessible repository and cited in the manuscript. If the grantee did not run a particular quality control test that appears in the table, they must explicitly state that the test was not run. For more information, see the [ASAP iPSC QC Reporting Template](#).
- 1.1.9. *Required. No new primary data statement*. If a study did not collect any new *primary data*, the Availability Statement (see [glossary](#)) must explicitly state that no new primary data were collected in the study. We *recommend* using the following boilerplate text: “No new primary data were collected in this study.” See [Section 3.3](#) for more information on Availability Statements and associated boilerplate text.

- 1.1.10. *Recommended. Folder and file structure.* For data types where a standard community-accepted file structure, folder structure, and/or specification exist, we *recommend* grantees use that structure or specification. For example, the [Brain Imaging Data Structure \(BIDS\)](#) for neuroimaging data and the [Neurodata Without Borders \(NWB\)](#) structure for neurophysiology data.

Required cases: ASAP Labs working with CatalystNeuro are *required* to use NWB format.

- 1.1.11. *Nice-to-have. Optional data types.* We encourage the sharing of quality control (QC) data, confirmatory data, and intermediate data (see [glossary](#)).

Required cases: iPSC quality control tables are *required* (see item 1.1.8)

1.2. Code

- 1.2.1. *Required. Code* (see [glossary](#)). Code generated by grantees must be deposited in a publicly accessible repository and issued a persistent identifier by the time of posting a preprint. This includes all scripts, software, packages, libraries, macros, pipelines, algorithms, executables, batch files, and any other code grantees wrote to manipulate data in any way, including but not limited to cleaning data, preprocessing data, analyzing data, and producing figures, tables, and results. This item applies to any grantee-generated code regardless of whether the code was written to be used primarily for a single study or for reuse by other researchers.

We *recommend* depositing code in a GitHub repository and then issuing a persistent identifier (e.g., a DOI) to the repository using Zenodo (instructions [here](#)). We *require* that Key Resources Tables cite a persistent identifier to the code as it was run for that study. We also *recommend* citing the GitHub URL, so that a reader can access any updates that were made to the code. Citing a GitHub URL alone is *not sufficient* because the content is not preserved and can be removed.

- 1.2.2. *Required. Reuse license (code).* Code must be deposited with a license that allows for distribution, modification, and unrestricted reuse. We *recommend* [the MIT License](#) (or another permissive license). Copyleft licenses are also *permitted* (e.g., [GNU General Public License](#)), and they are required if copying code published with a copyleft license. Note, code uses a different licensing system than manuscripts and data (and that is why we recommend an MIT License rather than a CC license).

- 1.2.3. *Required. **README file (code).*** Each code deposit must include a README file entitled “README”, located in the main folder of the deposit. README files must include sufficient information such that someone not part of the study team can access the code, determine which scripts execute which functions (e.g., clean data, produce figures), and understand the scripts well enough to rerun them and to integrate them into other code. Guidance is available [here](#).
- 1.2.4. *Required. **Computational environment.*** Code deposits must include a file that lists the session information, packages and their version numbers, and any other information needed to recreate the computational environment in which the code was run. This item can be met in several ways. For example, by creating a *renv.lock* file in R, a *requirements.txt* file in Python, a conda environment.yml file, or a Dockerfile.
- 1.2.5. *Required. **AI Models.*** For the purposes of this policy, grantee-generated AI models are considered a combination of code and data, which must be deposited together, and be usable by other researchers. This policy item applies, but is not limited, to both generative (Large Language Models–LLMs, AI agents) and predictive AI models. We *recommend* depositing large AI models and predictive framework applications that exceed Github storage limits to [Hugging Face](#). [See here](#) for guidance.
- 1.2.6. *Required. **No code statement.*** If grantees did not generate any code for their study, they must mention so in the Availability Statement (see [Section 3.3](#)). We *recommend* using the following boilerplate text: “*No code was generated for this study; all data cleaning, preprocessing, analysis, and visualization was performed using [insert program name(s)]*”. If even a few lines of code were entered into the command line or a program, we consider this to be code; it should be shared, and in that instance, this no code statement does not apply and therefore should not be used.
- 1.2.7. *Required (if specifically requested by ASAP staff, otherwise recommended). **Point-and-click workflows.*** When cleaning data, preprocessing data, analyzing data, and producing figures, tables, and results *without* the use of scripts, ASAP staff may request that grantees deposit (e.g., to protocols.io or Zenodo) a detailed and unambiguous explanation outlining how they performed these steps. The deposit may include project files (e.g., Prism files), screenshots, screen-capture videos, step-by-step written instructions, and/or other relevant materials.
- 1.2.8. *Recommended. **Computational notebook.*** We *recommend* that code is shared as computational notebooks (for example, Jupyter notebooks or RMarkdown), which combine code, narrative text explaining what the code is doing, and the outputs of the code – such as tables, plots, and

results. Code that is not shared as a notebook should contain sufficient comments to achieve the same benefits of a computational notebook.

- 1.2.9. *Nice-to-have. Reproducible container.* This allows the code to be run without needing to download materials or install software or packages. This can be achieved using a website like codeocean.com, a Jupyter notebook or a Docker container.

1.3. Protocols

- 1.3.1. *Required. Unpublished protocols* (see [glossary](#)). For all protocols that are mentioned in a manuscript but are not already associated with a persistent identifier that links to recipe-style instructions (see [glossary](#)), grantees must create a recipe-style protocol, deposit the protocol to receive a persistent identifier (e.g., DOI) (we *recommend* using protocols.io), and cite the persistent identifier in the manuscript and/or Key Resources Table (KRT). See the [glossary](#) for a detailed explanation of published versus unpublished protocols. Additional guidance is available [here](#).

Exception: We consider *in silico* methods to be code (these requirements are outlined in [Section 1.2](#)).

- 1.3.2. *Required. Reuse license (protocols).* Protocols must be deposited with a CC BY license or CC0 public domain dedication. “ND”, “NC”, and “SA” modifiers on the CC BY license are *not permitted*.

1.4. Lab Materials

- 1.4.1. *Required. Organism Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs).* Grantees must register an RRID for the following newly-generated organisms: [mouse](#), [rat](#), [zebrafish](#), and [Drosophila](#). Guidance for registering these novel organisms is located in the [SciCrunch Resource Citation Guidelines](#).

- 1.4.2. *Required. Cell line RRIDs.* Grantees must register an RRID for newly-generated stable cell lines. This includes cell lines that have been engineered with CRISPR/Cas9, Zinc Finger Nucleases, and Transcription Activator-like Effector Nucleases (TALEN) gene-editing processes. We *recommend* registering cell lines at [Cellosaurus](https://cellosaurus.org) by emailing cellosaurus@sib.swiss.

Exception: We do *not require* that transient cell lines are registered, as they are not stable cell lines. For example, cell lines engineered to (over)express a transgene through an expression vector (e.g.,

alpha-synuclein-GFP overexpression via a lentiviral expression procedure).

Exception: We also do *not require* that primary cell lines are registered due to their limited lifespan, and because they are also not considered stable cell lines. For example, primary neuronal cultures do not need to be registered with an RRID.

- 1.4.3. **Required. Plasmid RRIDs.** Grantees must register and deposit newly-generated plasmids at [Addgene](https://www.addgene.org). Addgene plasmids are registered RRID items in the format of RRID:Addgene_#####. See <https://www.addgene.org/deposit> for more information.

Exception: Viral tools developed at commercial entities using ASAP funds (e.g., Vector Builder) are often not able to be deposited at Addgene. In these instances, we *recommend* sharing the complete vector sequence and catalog number.

Exception: When reporting the use of plasmids that were generated by a collaborator, we *recommend* grantees encourage the collaborator to deposit the plasmid at Addgene. If the plasmid is not deposited, we *recommend* grantees report the origin of replication, antibiotic resistance gene, and promoter region.

- 1.4.4. **Required. Antibody RRIDs.** Grantees must register an RRID for newly-generated antibodies at the [Antibody Registry](https://www.abcam.com/antibody-registry).

Exception: Antibodies developed at commercial entities using ASAP funds (e.g., AbCam through the ASAP/MJFF tools program) may be registered by the commercial entity directly rather than by the grantee.

Exception (for items 1.4.1 – 1.4.4): Grantees are not required to register key lab materials they did not generate.

- 1.4.5. **Required. Lab Material Deposition.** If an ASAP grant contract includes a clause naming “Core/Repository Co-Investigator” and/or “Deposited Key Laboratory Materials” (e.g., in section 7c of the grant contract), then we require that grantees physically deposit their lab material in accordance with the contract (e.g., model organism, cell line, plasmid, antibody, reagent). In some documentation, these lab materials are referred to as “Tools”. This policy item supersedes policy items 1.4.1 – 1.4.4.

- 1.4.6. **Nice-to-have. Open Material Transfer Agreement (MTA).** The MTA associated with newly-generated key lab materials can be open. A template Open MTA is available [here](#).

1.5. Study Registration

- 1.5.1. *Required. Study registration (trials and replication studies).* We *require* that interventional research involving the collection of new data from human participants be registered at clinicaltrials.gov or [a primary registry in the WHO registry network](#). This requirement is in line with item 35 of [the WMA Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Participants](#) and the [International Committee of Medical Journal Editors \(ICMJE\) Recommendations](#). We also *require* registration of studies that include a primary aim to replicate a previous finding.
- 1.5.2. *Recommended. Study registration (general).* We *recommend* all hypothesis-driven and confirmatory research be registered in a community-recognized registry before data collection begins. In the case that data already exist, registration should occur before data analysis begins. We recommend using the [Open Science Framework \(OSF\) Preregistration Template](#) and registering at osf.io/registries. We also encourage registration of studies that are exploratory and not hypothesis-driven. We discourage, but *permit*, placing an embargo on a study registration. Registration is also variously called preregistration, prospective registration, and clinical trial registration. Deviating from a registered study plan or analysis is acceptable and should be transparently reported in the associated manuscript.

2. Identify Research Inputs

Summary. Data, software, protocols, and key lab materials used in a study—but which were not generated as part of an ASAP-funded study—must be unambiguously identified.

2.1. Published Data

- 2.1.1. *Required. Persistent identifiers.* All data used in a study—but which were not generated as part of the study—must be cited using a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI or accession number). It must be clear which data at that persistent identifier were used.

Exception. If a persistent identifier does not exist for the dataset being used, please include a link to the repository webpage, release number (if applicable), and the date accessed.

- 2.1.2. *Required. Access instructions.* If the data are not openly available, the manuscript must include information on how a reader can access the data and contact information for requesting access. This information should go in the Additional Information column of a manuscript's Key Resources Table.

2.2. Published Software

- 2.2.1. *Required. Programs* (e.g., GraphPad Prism, ImageJ; see [glossary](#)). All programs used in a study must be unambiguously identified. The Key Resources Table must include (1) the program version number, if one exists, (2) the program name, and (3) a URL, DOI, or persistent identifier where information about the program can be found.
- 2.2.2. *Required. Discipline-specific packages* (see [glossary](#)). For all discipline-specific packages, the Key Resources Table must include (1) the version number, if one exists, (2) the package name, and (3) a URL, DOI, or persistent identifier where information about the program can be found.
- 2.2.3. *Required. Generalist packages* (see [glossary](#)). We *require* that generalist packages be listed alongside the deposited code, as outlined in item 1.2.4 (computational environment). They must include at least (1) the version number, and (2) the package name. We do *not require* that generalist packages be listed in the manuscript or Key Resources Table.
- 2.2.4. *Recommended. RRIIDs (software).* We *recommend* including RRIIDs for all programs and discipline-specific packages. RRIIDs can be found by searching [RRID.site](#).

2.3. Published Protocols

- 2.3.1. *Required. Published protocols* (see [glossary](#)). For all protocols mentioned in a manuscript where recipe-style instructions already exist (i.e., published protocols), the manuscript must include (i) a DOI to the protocol, (ii) an explanation of what steps of the protocol were followed (this could be a statement that all steps were followed), and (iii) whether any modifications were made, and if so, what those modifications are (this could be a statement that no modifications were made). If a grantee made substantial modifications to a protocol, we *recommend* they [fork the protocol](#) (if it already exists on protocols.io), or publish a new protocol.

2.4. Pre-existing Key Lab Materials

- 2.4.1. *Required. RRIIDs (key lab materials).* Key lab materials (see [glossary](#)) including organisms, cell lines, plasmids, viruses, and antibodies must be

identified with a source/vendor, catalog number, and RRID. If an RRID does not exist, the Key Resources Table must explicitly state that an RRID does not exist.

- 2.4.2. *Required. Shared materials.* Grantees are *required* to include source information for key lab materials that were shared (e.g., material name, donor lab, and donor institution). We *recommend* that grantees discuss registering these materials with the donor lab, but recognize that this may be outside a grantee's control if the donor lab is not part of our ASAP network.

3. Ensure Immediate Open Access

Summary. Preprints must be posted no later than the date a manuscript is submitted to a journal for review. Preprints and publications must be immediately publicly available with a CC BY license or CC0 public domain dedication and include an Availability Statement and Key Resources Table (KRT) outlining where all research outputs (Requirement 1) and research inputs (Requirement 2) can be accessed.

3.1. Preprints

- 3.1.1. *Required. Preprints.* A preprint must be submitted to bioRxiv or medRxiv no later than the time a manuscript is submitted to a journal. ArXiv is an appropriate venue for preprints that are primarily computational.
- 3.1.2. *Required. Reuse license (preprints).* Preprints must come with a CC BY license or CC0 public domain dedication. “ND”, “NC”, and “SA” modifiers on the CC BY license are *not permitted*.
- 3.1.3. *Required. Copyright retention (preprints).* Authors must retain copyright of their preprint or waive the copyright through a CC0 public domain dedication.

Exception: U.S. Government employees may waive the copyright via a [U.S. Government Works public domain dedication](#).

- 3.1.4. *Required. Funder metadata (preprints).* The bioRxiv and medRxiv submission portals feature a “Funding Information” tab with two metadata fields: *Funding Body* and *Award Number*. We require that “*Aligning Science Across Parkinson’s*” be entered for the Funding Body and that the grant number, in the format *ASAP-000000*, be entered for the Award Number. To do so, start typing “*Aligning*”, and select the auto-completion option, “*Aligning Science Across Parkinson’s, Chevy Chase, US*”. Beginning in January 2026, these metadata fields are the primary way ASAP Staff track preprints from CRN researchers.

- 3.1.5. **Required. Preprint links to publication DOI.** Upon having a manuscript accepted for publication in a journal and receiving a DOI, grantees must ensure the preprint links to the journal publication DOI. BioRxiv and medRxiv generally make this link automatically. However, if the link is not made within 2-3 weeks of publication, we ask that you email biorxiv@openrxiv.org to request that they link the journal publication to your preprint (see bioRxiv FAQ: [My preprint has now been published in a journal. What happens next?](#)). Beginning in January 2026, this preprint linkage is the primary way ASAP Staff track original research publications from CRN researchers.
- 3.1.6. **Required. Revised preprints** (see [glossary](#)). After authors update their manuscript to address feedback from peer reviewers and ASAP Staff, the revised manuscript must be deposited as a new version of the preprint. The revised preprint must be deposited before the manuscript receives a DOI from a journal; once a manuscript receives a DOI from a journal, it may no longer be possible to post a revised preprint.

ASAP Staff will use the revised preprint as the reference point to assess whether a study is compliant with the ASAP Open Science Policy. If a revised preprint with all research outputs deposited *and* publicly available is not available within 6 months of the first version of the preprint, ASAP Staff will deem the manuscript not fully compliant with this Policy. If there are substantive updates to the data, analyses, results, or conclusion of a preprint—even if after ASAP Staff have deemed the preprint compliant with this Policy—then a new version of the preprint that reflects these changes must be posted.

Exception. If the initial preprint is compliant with the ASAP Open Science Policy, and there were no substantive updates to the data, analyses, results, or conclusions in response to peer review, then a revised preprint is *not required*.

3.2. Journal Publications

- 3.2.1. **Required. Immediate open access.** Journal publications must be made immediately publicly accessible with no embargo period. Immediate open access can be achieved by publishing in an open access journal, by posting the Author Accepted Manuscript (see [glossary](#)) to a publicly-accessible, community-recognized repository with no embargo period (e.g., PubMed Central, institutional repository), or by posting the Author Accepted Manuscript as a revised preprint. Posting to a non-permanent location is *not sufficient* (e.g., a researcher’s lab website).

- 3.2.2. *Required. Reuse license (publications).* Publications must come with a CC BY license or CC0 public domain dedication. “ND”, “NC”, and “SA” modifiers on the CC BY license are *not permitted*.
- 3.2.3. *Required. Preprint DOI in the publication.* In the publication, (i) indicate that a preprint exists, (ii) include the preprint DOI, and (iii) include the date when Version 1 of the preprint was posted. This information could go in the Acknowledgements section of a publication, the Availability Statement, or elsewhere, depending on the section headers used by the journal. We *recommend* the language: “An earlier version of this manuscript was posted to [preprint server] on [date] at [DOI].” This allows for unambiguous matching of preprints to journal publications.

3.3. Availability Statement

- 3.3.1. *Required. Availability statement.* Preprints and Publications must include an Availability Statement (see [glossary](#)) outlining where all the data, code, protocols, and key lab materials from Requirement 1 (research outputs) and Requirement 2 (research inputs) can be accessed. The Availability Statement must point to a Key Resources Table that contains this information.

Availability Statements that state that data, code, and/or protocols are available upon request are *not sufficient*.

If the ASAP Open Science Team is sent a manuscript without an Availability Statement, they will return it to the grantee and ask for an updated version that includes an Availability Statement before conducting compliance review. Guidance for creating an ASAP-compliant Availability Statement is [available here](#).

- 3.3.2. *Recommended. Boilerplate Availability Statement.* We *recommend* the following text be included in an Availability Statement, depending on which outputs were generated in the study:

“The data, code, protocols, and key lab materials used and generated in this study are listed in a Key Resources Table alongside their persistent identifiers at [enter the Zenodo DOI or Table number].”

“No code was generated for this study; all data cleaning, preprocessing, analysis, and visualization was performed using [insert program name(s)].”

“No new primary data were collected in this study.”

“An earlier version of this manuscript was posted to [preprint server] on [date] at [DOI].”

3.4. Key Resources Table

- 3.4.1. **Required. Key Resources Table (KRT).** We *require* that all preprints and journal publications cite, or include as a main manuscript table (i.e., not a supplementary table), a publicly available KRT that outlines all research outputs and research inputs. We *require* the KRT is an ASAP-formatted KRT ([see here for instructions](#)).

If a research output does not yet have a persistent identifier (e.g., the dataset is undergoing quality control at a repository), then we *require* that the KRT names the repository where the research output has been submitted and the date it was submitted. Thus, KRTs must list *all* data, code/software, protocols, and key lab materials, regardless of the manuscript stage (draft, preprint, publication), and even if the outputs are not yet publicly available. Beginning in January 2026, KRTs are the primary way that ASAP Staff track data, code, protocols, and key lab materials generated by CRN researchers.

If the ASAP Open Science Team is sent a manuscript without a KRT, or with a KRT that is missing key research outputs without justification (e.g., no data are identified in the KRT) they will return the manuscript to the grantee and ask for an updated version that includes a detailed KRT before conducting compliance review.

Exception: If publishing in a journal that has their own KRT format (e.g., Cell Press, eLife), then the publication may include a KRT in the format specified by that journal. Nonetheless, we still require that the Availability Statement points to an ASAP-formatted KRT (e.g., deposited to Zenodo).

4. Acknowledge ASAP

Summary. Manuscripts and other research outputs that were partially or fully funded by ASAP must acknowledge ASAP. Manuscripts must include an ORCID and a CRN author affiliation for CRN researchers.

4.1. Funding Acknowledgement

- 4.1.1. **Required. Funding (manuscripts).** ASAP must be acknowledged as a source of funding for all preprints and publications. This applies regardless of whether the preprints and journal publications are posted or published during the funding period or after the funding period has ended. The ASAP Research Organization Registry (<https://ror.org/03zj4c476>) and

ASAP grant number(s) must be included. We *recommend* the following language:

“This research was funded by Aligning Science Across Parkinson’s (<https://ror.org/03zj4c476>) [Insert grant number(s) e.g., ASAP-000000] through The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson’s Research (MJFF) (<https://ror.org/03arq3225>).”

- 4.1.2. **Required. Funding (research outputs).** ASAP must be acknowledged as a source of funding for all deposited data, code, protocols, and key lab materials. This applies regardless of whether data, code, protocols, and key lab materials are deposited or registered during the funding period or after the funding period has ended. The grant number(s) must be included.

For repositories with dedicated metadata fields for identifying funding organizations and grant numbers, grantees must use the metadata fields (e.g., Zenodo, protocols.io). For repositories that allow free-text to identify funding organizations and grant numbers, we *recommend* to include the text provided below (e.g., GitHub README file, GEO description field). For repositories that have neither a metadata field, nor a free-text field where funding organizations and grant numbers can be identified, we *require* that you link to a preprint or journal publication that acknowledges ASAP and the Team’s ASAP grant number (e.g., Addgene, Cellosaurus).

“This research was funded by Aligning Science Across Parkinson’s (<https://ror.org/03zj4c476>) [Insert grant number(s) e.g., ASAP-000000] through The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson’s Research (MJFF) (<https://ror.org/03arq3225>).”

4.2. ASAP Affiliation

- 4.2.1. **Required. ASAP CRN affiliation.** For preprints and publications, the ASAP CRN must be listed as an affiliation for all authors who are part of the Collaborative Research Network (defined as individuals listed on the [ASAP CRN Hub](#) and/or on a Team’s roster) with the following wording: *“Aligning Science Across Parkinson’s (ASAP) Collaborative Research Network, Chevy Chase, MD, 20815.”* For data, code, protocol, and key lab material deposits, listing the ASAP CRN as an affiliation is *recommended*.

4.3. ORCIDs

- 4.3.1. **Required. ORCIDs (manuscripts).** Preprints and publications must include [ORCIDs](#) (Open Researcher and Contributor IDentifiers) for all authors who are part of the Collaborative Research Network (defined as

the people on the [ASAP CRN Hub](#) and/or on a Team's roster). We *recommend* that all authors include their ORCID, regardless of whether they are affiliated with ASAP. Beginning in January 2026, the ORCIDs used in preprints will be the primary way ASAP Staff track the preprints associated with individual CRN researchers.

- 4.3.2. *Recommended. ORCIDs (research outputs).* We *recommend* that data, code, protocol, and key lab material deposits include ORCIDs. In particular, for repositories where a specific ORCID metadata field exists (e.g., Zenodo).

5. Share Outputs with the ASAP Network

Summary. All ASAP-funded research outputs, including manuscripts, must be promptly shared on the ASAP CRN Hub. Manuscript drafts must be sent to the ASAP Open Science Team through the ASAP CRN Hub no later than the time of posting a preprint.

5.1. Compliance Review

- 5.1.1. *Required. Compliance review.* Manuscripts must be submitted for compliance review (see [glossary](#)) using the [ASAP CRN Hub](#) Compliance Submission System by the time of posting a preprint (which must occur no later than the time of submission to a journal). [See here](#) for more information on submitting via the Hub.
- 5.1.2. *Required. Response to compliance review.* After addressing the comments raised in a compliance review, grantees must submit an updated version of the manuscript using the [ASAP CRN Hub](#) Compliance Submission System. The updated version must include an itemized response explaining how the authors addressed each comment raised in the compliance review. We *recommend* responding to the compliance review within 60 calendar days.

5.2. ASAP Hub

- 5.2.1. *Required. Upload to the ASAP CRN Hub.* Preprint DOIs must be uploaded to the Hub as a *Shared Research Output* within 5 business days of posting a preprint. Research outputs (data, code, protocols, and key lab materials) must be uploaded to the Hub as *Shared Research Outputs* in a timely manner, and no later than the time of journal publication.

Additional Notes

- **Spirit of the Policy.** We will consider a requirement to be unmet if actions are taken that are not in line with the spirit of the ASAP Open Science Policy. For example, if a protocol uploaded to protocols.io consists of blocks of text that were copy-pasted directly from the manuscript text rather than written in recipe-style; if a data deposit contains only summary data; or if a README file exists but contains almost no information, then the requirement is not considered to be met.
- **Grantee responsibility.** It is ultimately the grantee's responsibility to ensure that they meet the Policy. The ASAP Open Science Team performs compliance review to help grantees make their manuscripts compliant with the Policy. However, because compliance review draws from the manuscript text, this process can only identify content that is mentioned in the text. For example, if a grantee used code to analyze their data, but they do not mention code or the associated software in their manuscript text, then compliance review may not ask for code to be shared. In this situation, the ASAP Open Science Policy nonetheless requires that the code be shared.
- **Supplementary material.** We do not consider the Supplementary Material section of a publication or preprint to be registered with a persistent identifier. For example, data stored in supplementary material generally does not come with a DOI. Placing data, code, and protocols in the Supplementary Materials section does not constitute depositing to a repository and receiving a persistent identifier.
- **Research funded in part by ASAP.** The Policy applies to both research that is funded in whole by ASAP and research that is funded in part by ASAP. If a grantee feels that they will be unable to bring a partially ASAP-funded manuscript into compliance with the Policy, they must request an exemption (see next bullet point).
- **Exemptions.** Exemptions from these policy items may be granted on a case-by-case basis by emailing openscience@parkinsonsroadmap.org with a clear justification for why the Policy item cannot, or should not, be followed in a particular circumstance. We ask that requests for exemptions be emailed to us as early as reasonably possible. Exemptions requested at the time of journal publication or after journal publication are unlikely to be granted.
- **Policy Adherence.** We expect grantees to make reasonable efforts to comply with the above requirements and we will work cooperatively to ensure understanding and continually reinforce best practices. Compliance will be monitored and evaluated at regular intervals; failure to take corrective action(s) after repeated attempts by ASAP to rectify issues related to open science will be taken into account for future funding opportunities and could result in withholding of annual disbursement of funds and/or other support mechanisms.

Appendix A. Policy for Non-Original Research Manuscripts

The ASAP Open Science Policy, as outlined in the main section of this document, pertains to original research from grantees within the CRN. Appendix A outlines where the Policy differs for non-original research. We often refer to these articles as thought leadership manuscripts and they can include reviews, commentaries, perspectives, communications, letters, and other article types that do not include the collection of new data nor a formal analysis of existing data. For the purposes of this policy, we consider protocol articles to be original research.

The text below outlines how the 5 overarching policy requirements from the ASAP Open Science Policy (as outlined in the main section of this document) apply to non-original research manuscripts. A checklist for authors is available [here](#).

- **Requirement 1. Share research outputs.** *Not applicable.* If data, code, protocols, or lab materials were generated, then we consider the manuscript to report on original research and deem it subject to the ASAP Open Science Policy as described in the main section of this document. This categorization holds even if the manuscript is being published in the review section of a journal.
- **Requirement 2. Identify research inputs.** *Recommended.* If any items from Requirement 2 apply to a non-original research manuscript, we *recommend* that the policy item be met.
- **Requirement 3. Ensure immediate open access.** Some items within Requirement 3 apply to non-original research manuscripts, as follows:
 - All items within 3.1, as well as item 3.2.4, are *nice-to-have*. Note that bioRxiv and medRxiv only accept original research. Thus, we suggest posting a preprint to an institutional repository or another service that accepts non-original research manuscripts.
 - Items 3.2.1 and 3.2.2 are *required* (i.e., immediate open access, reuse license for publications).
 - Items within 3.3 and 3.4 are *not required*.

- **Requirement 4. Acknowledge ASAP.** All items are *required*, except for 4.1.2 and 4.3.2, which are *not applicable*.
- **Requirement 5. Share outputs with the ASAP network.** As for original research manuscripts, all items are *required*.

Appendix B. Glossary

Policy Levels

The ASAP Open Science Policy uses six specific terms to describe the policy items: *Required*, *Recommended*, *Nice-to-have*, *Permitted*, *Not permitted*, and *Exception*. We use each of these terms with a specific definition.

Required

Definition. If a *required* item is not met, we consider the related output (e.g., publication, data deposit) to be non-compliant with the Policy. Each *required* item comes with a workflow that the ASAP Open Science team employs to assess whether the item has been met.

Related terms. In relevant documents, we may also use the terms *must* or *ensure* to indicate that an item is required. For example, “to make this output compliant, a researcher *must*...” or “We ask that researchers *ensure* that...”.

Recommended

Definition. ASAP advises that grantees comply with *recommended* items. However, the ASAP Open Science Team will not systematically check that all recommended items are met. An output can be fully compliant, even if *recommended* items have not been met.

Related terms. We may also use the terms *should* or *encourage* to indicate that an item is recommended.

Nice-to-have

Definition. Items that are *nice-to-have* can be thought of as items that ASAP encourages, but not as strongly as a *recommendation*. This term could be used in a few different contexts. For example, to encourage aspirational practices or for practices which ASAP has yet to establish a clearly operationalized recommendation or requirement.

Permitted

Definition. Items that are *permitted* are considered in line with the ASAP Open Science Policy. However, we often use this term in a context where the policy recommends another option. For example, we *require* a reuse license for code, and *recommend* the MIT license. However, we also *permit* copyleft licenses. Both these options would be compliant with the Policy.

Not Permitted

Definition. *Not permitted* can be thought of as the inverse of *required*. The absence of something that is *required* can also be considered *not permitted*. This term can be useful to provide additional specification about specific policy items. For example, we require that preprints come with a CC BY license or CC0 public domain dedication, and the “ND” modifier on the license is *not permitted*.

Related terms. In some text, the term *not sufficient* may be used.

Exception

Definition. *Exceptions* indicate specific conditions where a *required* item does not need to be fully met for an output to be compliant with the Policy; or when an item that is *not required* must be addressed to be compliant with the Policy.

Data Types

Raw Data

Raw data, also known as primary data, are data in the initial form they were captured. They have not yet been preprocessed or cleaned. They are appropriate to deposit to a discipline-specific repository. For example, the [ASAP CRN Cloud](#), GEO (Gene Expression Omnibus), SRA (Sequence Read Archive), DANDI (Distributed Archives for Neurophysiology Data Integration), or OpenNeuro (more information on data repositories is available [here](#)).

Some discipline-specific repositories may require raw data to undergo some degree of preprocessing or cleaning before being deposited. The ASAP Open Science Policy requires data to be deposited in the ‘rawest reasonable format’ in which it makes sense to share data. The rawest reasonable format will generally be defined as the format in which a discipline-specific repository requires data to be deposited.

Cleaned Data

Cleaned data are the data entered into an analysis script and may represent the individual data points displayed in figures. Cleaned data originate from raw data. The amount of preprocessing and cleaning that occurs will vary greatly depending on the data type. Cleaned data are often in tabular format and can be uploaded to generalist data repositories like Zenodo or Dryad. Some discipline-specific repositories may also allow cleaned data to be deposited alongside raw data.

Cleaned data are not that same as *summary data* (see below). For the purposes of the ASAP Open Science Policy, in the context of image quantification, we consider the image files to be the raw data, and the image quantification to be the cleaned data.

Some researchers in the life sciences also use the term *source data* or *processed data* to describe what this document calls cleaned data.

Summary Data

We define *summary data* as the data that summarize more than one observation (e.g., means, standard deviation). These values may appear in figures and tables or as other numbers in the results section of a manuscript. Sharing these data can be useful, because the exact numbers are not always visible in figures. We consider *summary data* to be the output of a statistical analysis, and *cleaned data* to be the input of that statistical analysis.

Sensitive Data

Sensitive data include data that contain personal information, such as protected health information, and any other data that is likely to negatively harm an individual or community if publicly released.

Open Data

Definition from [data.bris](https://data.bris.ac.uk/): Open data is the most permissive data access level and is used for data which has no particular sensitivities. Where research participants are involved, they have given consent to share anonymised data as 'Open' data; the risk of re-identification of participants is considered to be extremely low. Open data is released under a re-use license.

Restricted Data

Definition from [data.bris](https://data.bris.ac.uk/): Restricted data has some degree of sensitivity involved. For example, research participants have not given explicit consent to share data as Open data. However, the risk of re-identification of participants is considered low. Data is made available to approved bona fide researchers only, after their host institution has signed a Data Access Agreement.

Controlled Data

Definition from [data.bris](https://data.bris.ac.uk/): Controlled data has a large degree of sensitivity involved. For example, research participants have not given explicit consent to share as Open data and/or the risk of re-identification of participants is medium to high. Requests for Controlled data are referred to an appropriate Data Access Committee for approval before data can be shared with bona fide researchers, after their host institution has signed a Data Access Agreement.

Note, after depositing restricted or controlled data, it is not the researcher who collected the data who decides who gets access, it is the organization that manages the data that makes these decisions

Quality Control (QC) Data / Confirmatory Data / Intermediate Data

The data collected to ensure the reliability, accuracy, and consistency of experimental results. This includes measurements and checks performed to validate sample integrity, instrument performance, and procedural accuracy. These data are used to identify and correct errors and to ensure that the data are trustworthy. Confirmatory data include many assays, such as chromatography, genotyping, and confirmatory sequencing. Intermediate data are produced part way through the process of converting raw data to cleaned data.

Code and Software

Figure 1. Schematic of the terminology the ASAP Open Science Policy uses regarding code. We use the term *code* to encompass all software, programs, packages, and scripts. We use *software* to indicate code that was written for reuse by others, and *scripts* to indicate code that was primarily written to clean and analyze the data from a particular study.

Scripts

These include all code that a researcher wrote to clean, curate, preprocess, analyze, visualize, or manipulate data in any way. We opt for the term script as opposed to ‘code’ to describe this because it may reduce ambiguity with the more broad use of code.

Software

We use this term to describe code that was written with the intention to be used more than once. For example, software may be maintained and designed to be used by others who were not involved in writing the software. Software includes both programs / commercial / consumer software (complete and executable) and packages (which extend the functionalities of programs). We discuss software in terms of (i) programs, (ii) discipline-specific packages, and (iii) generalist packages (defined below).

Program

Software that is made by a company, open source community, or individual that is executable on its own. The software is designed to be used by others and may include a Graphical User Interface–GUI. For example: GraphPad Prism, ImageJ, Fiji, R, Python, Matlab, STAR (Spliced Transcripts Alignment), FastQC, SAMtools.

Discipline-specific Package

Packages are collections of code that developers have written to add specific functionalities to programs like R, Python, and Matlab. If the package serves a specific scientific purpose, we call that a *discipline-specific package*. For example: MetaPhlAn 3.0, AccuSleep, MERINGUE, Slingshot.

Generalist Package

These are packages that were not designed for a specific scientific discipline. For example, the package *tidyverse* was made to make coding more streamlined and *ggplot* was made to plot various types of data. For example: dplyr, ggplot, tidyverse, kable, numpy, pandas.

Protocols

Recipe-style Instructions

We define recipe-style instructions as clearly written documentation on how to perform a particular protocol, procedure, methodology, or technique. Recipe-style instructions will often include a list of all the lab materials required and a step-by-step explanation of what to do. We only consider documents where the writing is specifically directed toward a reader who is trying to repeat that protocol to be recipe-style instructions. Guidance is available [here](#).

Published Protocol

We consider a protocol to be published if an identifier (e.g., DOI, URL) exists that brings a reader to *recipe-style instructions*. Published protocols can include:

- Protocols on repositories like protocols.io.
- Protocol articles or methods articles (e.g., articles in journals like *STAR Protocols* and *Nature Methods*).
- Manufacturers' instructions.
- Outsourced procedures.

Note, if you cannot provide an identifier that a reader can follow and arrive at recipe-style instructions for any of the four types of protocols listed above, then we consider them *unpublished protocols*.

Unpublished Protocol

We consider a protocol to be unpublished if there is not an identifier that can bring a reader to *recipe-style instructions*. Unpublished protocols can include:

- Protocols that your team developed, but have not yet deposited to a repository like protocols.io.
- Methods outlined in regular research articles.
- Protocols that were developed based on a published protocol, but contain substantial modifications (i.e., where it would be easier to write a new or “[forked](#)” [protocol](#), rather than list every modification).
- Protocols with several steps, even when some of those steps are to follow a specific manufacturer’s instructions.
- Outsourced procedures.

Forked Protocol

On [protocols.io](#), there is an option to “fork” a protocol. This allows a user to copy a published protocol, edit the text, and then publish a modified version of the protocol that will be linked to the original version of protocol. We encourage forking because it provides a clear link to the original protocol.

Lab Materials

Key Lab Materials

Key lab materials include organisms, cell lines, plasmids, viruses, and antibodies. ASAP’s Open Science Policy requires that manuscripts report RRIDs for key lab materials. *Other* lab materials include kits, reagents, hardware, and primers.

Other Terms

Availability Statement

We use the term Availability Statement broadly to encompass any and all sections of a manuscript that appear under a header that is specifically related to the availability of data, code, protocols, and/or lab materials. These section headers could be: Data Availability, Data and Code Availability, Materials Availability, Resource Availability, Open Science Practices, or contain other relevant terms.

For example, the journal *Cell* requires both a Data and Code Availability Statement and a Materials Availability Statement. We use the term *Availability Statement* to encompass both of these manuscript sections.

ASAP-funded Work

ASAP funds are project-based, meaning they are given to each team based on the work they proposed. ASAP-funded work should relate to the team's proposed project and consists of any of the following:

- Projects that are listed in the ASAP-funded proposal.
- Methods or resource papers that enable the ASAP-funded proposal.
- Pivots stemming from the findings of the ASAP-funded proposal.
- Thought leadership pieces (reviews, communications, letters) on the topic that the ASAP-funded proposal aims to address.

Compliance Review

This is the process where a member of the ASAP Open Science Team performs a systematic check to see whether a manuscript is compliant with the ASAP Open Science Policy. This process consists of an automatic compliance check performed by dataseer.ai and a manual check from an ASAP Open Science team member. ASAP then sends the grantee the output from the automated dataseer report and a written list of actions that would be necessary to bring the manuscript into compliance with the ASAP Open Science Policy.

Manuscript

We use the term manuscript to refer to a document reporting a research study. This definition includes all of the following: a draft that is not yet publicly shared, a preprint, a publication.

Revised Preprint

BioRxiv and medRxiv preprints can be updated. The DOI will always point to the most recent version of the preprint. Readers are also able to access all the earlier versions of a preprint. A revised preprint is a preprint that has been updated with new information, for example, after addressing peer reviewer comments.

Author Accepted Manuscript

An Author Accepted Manuscript is the version of a manuscript which a journal has accepted for publication. These manuscripts are in the format in which the author submitted them to a journal for review and which the journal has not typeset nor copyedited.

Original Research

We define original research as any piece of research that includes the collection of new data or a formal analysis of existing data. Original research is subject to all items in the ASAP Open Science Policy. Non-original research includes reviews, communications, letters, and thought leadership pieces that do not include the collection of new data nor a formal analysis of existing data. For the purposes of this policy, we consider protocol articles to be original research.